

where o is organic phase, a the aqueous phase and R_4N^+ is Aliquat-336.

Analysis of mercury in soil samples : The present method has been applied for the determination of mercury in several soil samples of Attri, Orissa. The results by the recommended procedure are as follows : sample-1 (81 ± 1 ppm), sample-2 (110 ± 3 ppm), sample-3 (108 ± 3 ppm), sample-4 (156 ± 4 ppm) and sample-5 (102 ± 2 ppm). The reliability of the present method was checked by studying the analytical recovery of mercury. The results for such determinations were found to be 96–103%.

References

1. R. OSLAND, *Spectrovision*, 1970, 24, 11.
2. Y. UMEZAKI and K. IWATOMOTO, *Bunseki Kagaku*, 1971, 20, 178.
3. R. V. D. ROBERT, *Inst. Metall. Repub. S. Afr. Rep.*, 1977, 13, 1872 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1977, 87, 47719).
4. H. GREEN, *Talanta*, 1973, 20, 189.
5. A. K. DE, U. S. RAY and N. PARI in "Environmental Management and Planning", ed. A. K. SEN, Wiley Eastern, New Delhi, 1988, p. 271.
6. S. BANDYOPADHYAY and A. K. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, 63, 283.
7. S. BANDYOPADHYAY and A. K. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, 63, 623.
8. "The Coordinated research programme to ensure the quality of marine products in relation to toxic elements: A report on mercury covering the period 1975-82", The Marine Products Export Development Authority, Cochin, India, 1985, p. 11.
9. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry, A Comprehensive Text", 3rd. ed., Interscience, New York, 1972, p. 518.

Spectrophotometric Determination of Iron(II) using Cacotheline

A. SARKAR, P. K. PARI* and S. K. MAJUMDAR
Department of Chemistry, North Bengal University,
Darjeeling-784 430

Manuscript received 7 March 1988, revised 26 October 1988,
accepted 6 April 1989

CACOTHELIN is to be the nitrate of the bisdimethylmononitrobrucine hydrate¹ and have the formula, $C_{20}H_{20}(OH)_2(NO_2)_2N_2O_3 \cdot HNO_3$. Aqueous solution of cacotheline gives a violet colour with stannous ions due to the formation of a reduction product of cacotheline of unknown composition². Potluri³ used cacotheline as an indicator in estimating Pb^{IV} and Cr^{VI} with Ti^{III} . The present authors noted that Fe^{II} gives a violet colour with aqueous solution of cacotheline in presence of phosphoric acid, and which lead to the development of a simple spectrophotometric method for iron(II) determination.

Experimental

Spectral curves and analytical measurements were made with a Shimadzu PR1 spectrophotometer

fitted with quartz cells of 10 mm optical path-length.

Stock solution of iron(II) was prepared from $FeSO_4 \cdot (NH_4)_2SO_4$ and standardised⁴; a working solution was prepared by appropriate dilution. Aqueous solution of cacotheline (0.2%) was used for colour development. All other reagents were of analytical grade. Stock solutions of diverse ions were prepared from their corresponding salts.

General procedure : To an aliquot containing 100–500 μg iron(II), was added phosphoric acid (5 ml) and the aqueous solution of cacotheline (0.5 ml). Volume of the mixture was made up to 10 ml with distilled water and the absorbance of the solution was measured at 530 nm against pure water as blank. Amount of iron(II) was computed from a calibration curve. To test the interference, the respective foreign ions were added to the system before addition of the reagents.

Results and Discussion

In presence of fluoride or phosphate, iron(II) gives a violet colour with cacotheline. In the former, the colour is very unstable and fades away within 5 min. But in presence of phosphoric acid the system gives a stable colour for at least 12 h showing a broad band of absorption maxima around 530 nm. The reagent blank does not absorb in this region.

It has been noted that 0.5 ml of 0.2% cacotheline is sufficient for maximum colour development of the sample solution containing upto 500 μg of iron(II) provided the aqueous solution be made 6–10 M with respect to phosphoric acid. Lower values in absorbance were obtained when the aqueous phase was less than 5 M with respect to phosphoric acid. Higher concentration of the reagent or the acidity of the aqueous phase were devoid of any significant change in the maximum value of absorbance. The system conforms to Beer's law over the concentration range 2–50 ppm of Fe^{II} with Sandell's sensitivity of 0.05 $\mu g cm^{-2}$ at 530 nm.

To test the interferences, iron(II) was determined in presence of the respective foreign ions. Deviation of not more than $\pm 3\%$ from the expected absorbance was taken as the standard tolerance limit for the system. It was found that 300 μg of Fe^{II} could easily be determined without any interference in presence of 5 mg of each of the following cations: Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Mo^{VI} , Pd^{II} , Pt^{IV} , Rh^{III} , Cd^{II} , Ca^{II} , Ba^{II} , Sr^{II} , Zr^{II} , Th^{IV} , Be^{II} , Zn^{II} , Hg^{II} , Mg^{II} , Pb^{II} , Tl^{I} , U^{VI} , La^{III} and Al^{III} . Cu^{II} and V^{V} must be absent as the system gives no colour in presence of the said cations. Presence of less than 2 mg of Cr^{III} is harmless. In presence of Fe^{III} low absorbance is obtained. The system tolerates 50 mg of each of the following anions: EDTA, thiosulphate, iodide, bromide, fluoride, citrate, tartrate, ascorbate, oxalate, acetate, phthalate, borate. There is no colour development if nitrate is present.

NOTES

The method is very simple and rapid. Precision and accuracy of the proposed method were tested by analysing solutions containing a known amount of iron(II). The average of six determinations of 300 μg Fe was found to be 300.5 μg with the relative mean deviation of 1.27%.

References

- 1 N. MOUFANG and J. TAPPEL, *Ann.*, 1898, 304, 47.
- 2 F. J. WELCHER, "Organic Analytical Reagents", Van Nostrand, Princeton, Vol. 3, 1962.
- 3 V. K. R. POTLURI, V. R. RAO and A. KUMAR, "Proceedings of the 24th Annual Convention of Chemists", Indian Chemical Society, Calcutta, 1987, p. D2.
- 4 A. I. VOGEL, "A Textbook of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans, London, 1978.